

Polymer Primer for CLEAR Lab

Authors

Dr Joseph Razzell Hollis

j.razzellhollis@gmail.com

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Introduction

This Primer was written by Dr Joseph Razzell Hollis to help students in the CLEAR Lab understand the chemical and practical differences between the various types of polymers commonly found in plastic pollution in Nunatsiavut, Canada, and how they can be distinguished from one another using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy.

Monitoring plastics depends on being able to distinguish plastics found in the environment from non-plastics. This is trivial when plastic objects are relatively large, intact, and/or clearly labelled, but as they break down through physical, chemical or biological weathering, they become harder to identify by visual assessment alone [Lenz *et al.*, 2015; Provencher *et al.*, 2017]. FTIR spectroscopy is a commonly used method for identifying plastics by their chemical composition and is routinely used in plastic pollution monitoring [Nichols *et al.* 1985; Chalmers & Everall, 1999; Mecozzi *et al.*, 2016], but some experience and knowledge is needed to correctly and reliably interpret FTIR spectra and even experts can still make errors. Many plastics share common motifs in chemical structure that make them appear similar in FTIR, which can be further complicated or modified by environmental factors such as age, weathering and contamination [Nichols *et al.*, 1985; Razzell Hollis *et al.*, 2024]. Understanding the range of spectra that may be encountered, both plastic and non-plastic, can help ensure a more robust, reliable interpretation of the data.

The types of polymers shown in this document are merely a subset of all plastics that are in use globally, though they do represent a significant proportion of global plastic production. The choice of polymers reflects the types of plastic pollution collected by a partnered plastic monitoring project in Nunatsiavut, Canada, between 2017 and 2024 [Pijogge *et al.*, 2025]. The project is a partnership between the Nunatsiavut Government, the CLEAR Lab at the Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador, and the Natural History Museum in the UK. FTIR spectra are (unless stated otherwise) of plastics found in Nunatsiavut and were measured at Surface Science Western at Western University. All data relating to plastics found in Nunatsiavut is owned and controlled by the Nunatsiavut Government and published only after community review.

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1. What Are Polymers?

Polymers are made of repeating organic molecules (monomers) that are chemically bound together into long chains. Because of the sheer variety of different organic molecules that can be chained together, there are many different types of polymers with different chemical and mechanical properties. These properties can be further modified by adding different monomers to the chain (known as copolymerisation), by changing the length of the chain (molecular weight), changing the way the chains fit together (crystallinity), or by adding small organic molecules (additives) to the final product. A wide range of easily controlled properties is one of the reasons why plastics are so popular for manufacturing. Polymers are not exclusively the product of industrial manufacturing, polymers can also be made by living organisms, including RNA and DNA (polymerised nucleotides), protein and collagen (polymerised amino acids), cellulose and starch (polymerised glucose), as well as natural rubber and resins.

Fig. 1.1: illustration showing the different chemical structures of several common polymers, highlighting the repeating unit (the monomer) in each case. Made by Joseph Razzell Hollis.

Polymers are usually named based on the molecules they are made from (e.g. polyethylene is made from the polymerisation of ethylene) though sometimes brand names are used (e.g. Nylon). Polymers are sometimes put into families/classes based on common chemical themes: both Nylon and protein are in the polyamide class because they use amide links for polymerisation, while polyethylene and polypropylene are in the polyolefin class because they are made from alkene monomers (also known as olefins).

Fig. 1.2: illustration showing different possible arrangements of repeating units for a linear chain co-polymer made of two monomers named A and B. Made by Joseph Razzell Hollis.

Polymers may be composed of more than one repeating unit: **homopolymers** are made of a single repeating unit, but **copolymers** are made of two or more repeat units. The different units in a copolymer can be randomly linked together (a **random copolymer**), alternate in a regular pattern (**alternating copolymer**), or come in discrete sections (**block copolymer**). ABS is an example of a copolymer made of 3 units: acrylonitrile, butadiene, and styrene.

Fig. 1.3: illustration showing simplified versions of possible structures that non-linear polymer chains can adopt depending on how they are connected. Made by Joseph Razzell Hollis.

Polymers may be linear or branching: depending on the polymerisation method used, polymers can end up as single **linear** chains with no branches, **branching** chains that split from side-chains at occasional intervals, or randomly **cross-linked** networks of highly interconnected chains. LLDPE is an example of a highly linear polymer, whereas epoxy tends to form cross-linked networks. Branches tend to reduce density, crystallinity.

Fig. 1.4: illustration showing the different possible ways that polymer chains can organise themselves depending on their overall crystallinity. Made by Joseph Razzell Hollis.

Polymers may be neatly arranged or a tangled mess: in **crystalline** plastics the polymer chains are lined up in neat rows that fit together side by side (like uncooked spaghetti), in **amorphous** plastics the chains are randomly arranged and tangled together (like cooked spaghetti). **Semi-crystalline** plastics contain a mix of amorphous and crystalline regions, usually nanoscale in size, with an overall crystallinity between 10 and 80%. Higher crystallinity is associated with greater density, strength and durability, but lower flexibility and elasticity.

Because of the slightly unpredictable nature of chemical reactions, most actual plastic objects will be made of trillions of polymer chains with slightly different compositions, lengths, and degrees of organisation. Manufacturers may also introduce additives and other polymers to regulate or modify a plastic's properties, and in extreme cases (for example, PVC-based

inflatables) additives may account for >50% of the material's total weight [British Plastics Federation, 2011].

As a rule, do not use an acronym as shorthand for a polymer unless it is already clearly in use in the literature or on Wikipedia. The reason for this is to avoid confusion, for example polyamide, polyacetal, polyacrylate are very different types of plastic whose names could reasonably be shortened to 'PA', and 'PA' is often used for different plastics in different contexts, so using 'PA' as shorthand can lead to confusion. Section 2 provides a non-exhaustive list of commonly used names for different polymers, including acronyms.

2. Polymer Reference Table

Class of Polymer	Subclass of Polymer	Common Names	Common Uses
Polyolefins	Polyethylene	PE (HDPE, LDPE, LLDPE)	Pipes, plastic bottles, plastic bags, food packaging, stretch wrap
	Polypropylene	PP	Furniture, pipes, containers, falcon tubes, textiles, crisp packets
	Polyvinyl Chloride	PVC	Pipes, vinyl flooring, banners, electrical insulation, inflatables
	Polystyrene	PS (also EPS, Styrofoam)	Cutlery, packaging foam, insulation, buoys
	Polyacrylonitrile	PAN (Acrylic in textiles)	Textiles, carbon fiber precursor
	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene	ABS	Toys, helmets, keyboards, appliances, Lego
	Polyvinyl Acetate	PVAc	Wood glue, latex paint binder, resin
	Polyacrylate	PMMA (Acrylic paint, glass, Lucite, Perspex), Superglue	Impact-resistant windows, paint, adhesives
Polyesters	Polyethylene Terephthalate	PET	Bottles, polyester textiles (Dacron, Mylar), insulation
	Alkyd	Alkyd resin	Oil-based paints, varnishes, enamels, coatings
Polyamides	Aliphatic Polyamides	Nylon (e.g., Nylon-6, Nylon-6,6)	Textiles, fishing lines, guitar strings
	Aromatic Polyamides	Aramid (e.g., Kevlar, Nomex)	Body armour, flame-resistant clothing, mooring ropes

Class of Polymer	Subclass of Polymer	Common Names	Common Uses
Polyurethanes	—	PU, PUR	Sponges, insulation, elastic textiles (Spandex, Lycra)
Polycarbonates	—	PC (Bisphenol A-based)	CDs, roofing, bottles, lab goggles, windows
Polyethers	—	POM (Acetal, Polyformaldehyde)	Gears, plumbing joints, toys, bearings, electrical insulation
Biological	Proteinaceous Polyamides	Protein	Keratin, collagen, biofilms
	Polysaccharides	Cellulose	Cotton, paper, cardboard
	Polysaccharides	Chitin	Insect shells, mollusc beaks, food/fertilizer additive
Semi-Synthetic	Cellulose Acetate	Cellulose Acetate	Cigarette filters, film stock
	Nitrated Cellulose	Nitrocellulose	Film stock, gun-cotton, lacquers
Tricky Categories	Epoxy Resins	Epoxy (e.g., BPA-based)	Coatings, adhesives, fibreglass/carbon composites
	Acrylic Paint, Acrylic Resin, Acrylic Glass, Acrylic Fibre	PAN, Polyacry	Paint, adhesive, glass, textiles

3. What is FTIR?

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy is an analytical method for identifying chemical compounds based on the distinct vibrations of their atomic bonds. Molecules can have several possible vibrations, which can involve the stretching, bending, rocking, and twisting of different bonds, or combinations thereof. Many (but not all) of these vibrations can be excited by absorbing infrared light, these 'IR-active' vibrations appear in FTIR spectra as absorption peaks at particular frequencies [Chalmers & Everall, 1999]. Peaks from vibrations of similar bonds in different molecules (i.e. C=O) will generally occur in certain known ranges but may differ slightly in actual frequency depending on the chemical structure surrounding them. As a result, each polymer will produce an infrared absorption spectrum that is highly specific to its chemical structure and can be used to distinguish it from seemingly identical materials made of different polymers (see Fig 3.1).

Fig. 3.1: Typical normalised FTIR spectra for four different polymers, showing distinct patterns of absorbance peaks along with assignments of major peaks to specific bond vibrations. Typical frequency ranges for important vibrations are shown above, coloured according to the CPK colouring schema for the atoms involved. Made by Joseph Razzell Hollis, spectral data from Nunatsiavut.

Vibrational frequencies are usually measured in wavenumbers (unit: cm^{-1}), but as wavelengths in microns (μm). FTIR spectra are generally recorded from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} , a range known as mid-infrared, range that captures most major fundamental vibrations. These are collectively grouped into two major regions: the skeletal region (100–1800 cm^{-1}) that includes vibrations of the organic skeleton, e.g. C–C, C=C, C=O, and the high frequency or hydrogen region (2700–3800 cm^{-1}) that includes vibrations involving hydrogen, e.g. C–H, O–H, N–H.

Absorbance cannot be measured directly, so instead it is measured from the change in either transmitted light from the sample (Transmittance FTIR) or reflected light (Reflectance FTIR). A common method is Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR-FTIR), where the sample is pressed against a special crystal window to enhance the signal quality, but this is often limited to relatively large (>1 mm) samples. The FT part of FTIR refers to the method of measuring the entire spectrum at once, and using a Fourier transform to then separate it based on frequency.

For samples containing more than one kind of molecule, FTIR shows us the total absorbance combined across all molecules present in the volume of the sample being analysed. This means we can detect peaks from both the bulk polymer and any additives present, weighted according to their proportion and their relative infrared absorption coefficients. For most plastics, where the bulk polymer is by far the most significant component of the material, the spectrum will be dominated by the polymer, but in some cases (e.g. flexible PVC) where additives may outweigh the polymer, FTIR peaks from the additives will be just as strong as peaks from the polymer itself.

3.1 FTIR vs Raman

Raman spectroscopy is a similar technique that uses a focused laser to excite scattering from molecular vibrations. Some types of vibrations are only detectable to FTIR and some are only detectable to Raman, the two techniques will give different spectra for the same sample (see Fig 3.2). Because of this, FTIR and Raman are considered complementary techniques. For analysing plastic pollution, FTIR tends to be more straight-forward in its application and interpretation and in at least one case (plastics ingested by sable shearwaters) FTIR outperforms Raman in terms of the fraction of samples that give identifiable spectra [Razzell Hollis *et al.*, 2024].

Fig. 3.2. FTIR vs Raman spectra obtained from the same piece of PE found in a sable shearwater's stomach [Razzell Hollis *et al.*, 2024]. Raman spectra were measured using 3 different lasers and baseline-subtracted for easier comparison.

4. Generic Material Terms

4.1 Resin

Resin does not refer to any specific class of chemical structures or polymers but is a catch-all term for viscous liquids that contain monomers or pre-polymers that may become polymerised to produce a solid. Natural resins include amber and shellac, synthetic resins include epoxy resins, polyacrylates such as PMMA, and alkyds (polyester resins). Technically resin only refers to the monomeric component (pre-polymerisation) but is often used for the final product as well. As a result, the term resin is less about chemistry and more about practical application – typically referring to the liquid/gel that is applied to create a solid plastic in place, through a coating process such as varnish or paint, as an adhesive, or casting solid objects using moulds.

4.2 Paint

Paints are anything containing pigments (chemicals that produce colour) that intended to be applied to a surface. Liquid paints generally use binding agents to keep the pigment attached to the surface once applied, and while natural agents have been used for most of history, in modern times binding agents are predominantly made of polymers. In **water-based (or latex) paints**, the most common binding agents are homopolymers or copolymers of acrylic resin (polyacrylate) or polyvinyl acetate (PVAc); acrylic paints specifically use polyacrylate. In **oil-based paints** the polymer is usually a polyester resin (alkyd) but can be polyurethane (PU) or epoxy resin. Many oil-based binding agents are also used to make synthetic varnishes, which are essentially paints that lack pigmentation and are transparent.

In the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset, we have 13 samples classed as paint. Most of these exhibit ester C=O peaks around 1730 cm^{-1} and are likely alkyds. However, not all alkyds are used in paint, and not all paint is made of alkyds.

4.3 Adhesive (glue)

Adhesives are substances that are applied to one or more surfaces to bind them together. Adhesives are typically applied as a liquid that then hardens, the hardening process can be driven by solvent evaporation (**drying adhesives**), by chemical reaction (**curing adhesives**),

or by cooling (**hot-melt adhesives**). Drying adhesives that use polymers include polyvinyl acetate (PVAc), commonly referred to as wood glue or white glue. Curing adhesives include polyurethane, acrylic resins (polyacrylate), and epoxy resins, and the polymerisation of cyanoacrylate forms the basis of superglue. Hot-melt adhesives include various thermoplastics but commonly use polyethylene vinyl acetate (PEVA) or polyolefins like LDPE. Adhesives therefore have substantial overlap with solid plastics, paints, and resins.

In the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset, we have 3 samples classed as adhesive by SSW. Most of these exhibit ester C=O peaks around 1730 cm^{-1} and are decent matches to PVAc, a commonly used polymer glue. All 3 have clay mineral peaks between 3600 and 3700 cm^{-1} , either due to the use of clay as a filler in the adhesive, or because some clay became adhered to the polymer once it entered the environment.

5. Polyolefins

Polyolefins are a class of plastics that use alkene polymerisation to produce a backbone of 2 repeating carbons. These are some of the simplest polymers (chemically speaking) and consequently include some of the earliest developed synthetic polymers, representing a large proportion of global plastic production to date [Geyer *et al.*, 2017].

5.1 Polyethylene (PE, also HDPE, MDPE, LDPE, LLDPE)

A commonly used polyolefin made from ethylene, PE accounts for ~36% of all global non-fibre plastic production since 1950. Common variants include high density (HDPE), medium density (MDPE), low density (LDPE), and linear low density (LLDPE), among others. HDPE is strong and durable, used to make pipes, house-wrap, plastic furniture, oil cans, and rigid plastic bottles, among others. LDPE and LLDPE are flexible and stretchy, used to make plastic bags, food packaging, garbage bags, and stretch-wrap. In Nunatsiavut we have directly identified PE in skidoo/motor oil bottles, shotgun cartridges and wadding, some (but not all) fishing line/rope, and in kamutik (sledge) runners, all of which were ID'd by Nunatsiavummiut.

PE is distinguished in FTIR by having only peaks associated with CH₂: two strong peaks at ~2850 and ~2920 cm⁻¹, a weak peak at ~720 cm⁻¹, and a weak peak at ~1470 cm⁻¹. In highly crystalline forms of PE, typically HDPE and LLDPE, the 720 and 1480 peaks may split into doublets due to in-phase/out-of-phase vibrations. HDPE can be distinguishable from LDPE using FTIR, but only under relatively controlled conditions. When dealing with environmental samples, it is more difficult to ascertain if observed variance between PE spectra is due to density or is the result of other confounding factors such as weathering or biological contamination.

5.2 Polypropylene (PP)

A commonly used polyolefin made from propylene, PP accounts for ~21% of all global non-fibre plastic production since 1950 [Geyer *et al.*, 2017]. Because the propylene unit has a methyl group ($-\text{CH}_3$) sticking out the side after polymerisation, PP comes in three forms depending on how the methyl groups are oriented: **isotactic** means they are all on the same side of the chain (which tends to produce crystalline plastic), **syndiotactic** means they are on alternating sides, and **atactic** means they are arranged at random (which tends to be amorphous). Most PP plastics are isotactic. PP is used in furniture, pipes, laboratory falcon tubes, rigid containers, and non-woven textiles, among others. PP is also the 4th most used plastic in textile fibres, mainly in industrial and fishing applications rather than clothing [Menyhárd *et al.*, 2020]. Metallicized PP is also commonly used in crisp/chip packets and in fishing line/rope.

PP is distinguished in FTIR by having only peaks associated with CH_2 and CH_3 : a set of 4 strong peaks at ~ 2850 and ~ 2920 cm^{-1} , and 2 weaker peaks at ~ 1380 and 1460 cm^{-1} . In several cases, we also observe a $\text{C}=\text{O}$ peak at ~ 1720 cm^{-1} that is not due to the PP chain but may be evidence of co-polymerisation with a $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bearing monomer, or degradation of pure PP (for example, burning or UV exposure).

5.3 Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC)

A commonly used polyolefin made from vinyl chloride, PVC (also known as vinyl) accounts for ~12% of global plastic production since 1950 [Geyer *et al.*, 2017]. PVC can vary from rigid plastic to highly flexible depending on the proportion of plasticiser additives used, which can be as high as 90% by mass. Rigid PVC is used in pipes and construction; semi-rigid PVC is used in vinyl flooring, stretch-wrap, and banners; flexible PVC is used in electrical insulation, clothing, and inflatables. Phthalate-based plasticisers are commonly used in PVC and tend to leach out of the plastic over time as they are not chemically bound to the bulk polymer.

In FTIR, pure PVC is distinguishable by a pair of CH and CH₂ peaks at ~2850 and ~2920 cm⁻¹, a CH peak at 1420 cm⁻¹, and a C-Cl peak at ~650 cm⁻¹. However, in flexible PVC the polymer spectrum may be dominated by peaks from the plasticiser. Phthalate plasticisers typically exhibit 3 CH peaks at ~2860, ~2930, and ~2960 cm⁻¹, an ester C=O peak at ~1730 cm⁻¹, and an ester C-O peak at ~1250 cm⁻¹. All 16 examples of PVC in the NG Plastics dataset are rich in phthalates, and 4 more samples classed as Phthalate exhibit very similar spectra.

5.4 Polystyrene (PS)

Another commonly used polyolefin, PS is made from styrene molecules and accounts for about 8% of global plastic production to date [Geyer *et al.*, 2017]. PS can be moulded into rigid sheets (used for disposable cutlery) or expanded into foam (used for disposable packaging, insulation, fishing buoys). A common form is expanded polystyrene (EPS, brand name Styrofoam), which is made of small foam beads that are packed and fused into the desired shape. Like PP, PS can be isotactic, syndiotactic, or atactic, but almost all commercial PS is atactic with randomly oriented side groups. PS is also a component of the copolymer ABS.

In FTIR, PS exhibits strong aromatic ring peaks from the side group as well as peaks from the ethylene backbone. The ethylene backbone produces a CH₂ peak at 1450 cm⁻¹ and two CH₂ peaks at 2850 and 2920 cm⁻¹. The aromatic ring produces a very strong peak at 700 cm⁻¹, a weaker peak at 750 cm⁻¹, two benzene ring peaks at 1490 and 1600 cm⁻¹, and a set of C-H peaks between 3000 and 3100 cm⁻¹. There is also a notable set of 4 weak fringe peaks between 1700 and 2000 cm⁻¹.

5.5 Styrene-Butadiene Rubber (SBR, Crumb Rubber)

SBR is a sub-class of co-polymers made from styrene and butadiene. SBR is a fully synthetic alternative to natural rubbers, used primarily in automotive tires, shoes, and gaskets. Less common uses for SBR include as a resin for coated paper and a sealing/binding agent in construction. Crumb rubber usually refers to recycled SBR, usually from old tires that are ground into granules/powder that can be moulded and fused into new forms.

There are two recorded instances of crumb rubber in the NG-Plastics dataset, but their FTIR spectra are no longer available.

5.6 Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)

PAN (not to be confused with polyaniline, known as PANI) is a commonly used polyolefin made from acrylonitrile. It is primarily used as fibres to make textiles though it is also a precursor in the manufacturing of carbon fibre. PAN is synonymous with acrylic in the textiles industry but in other contexts acrylic may refer to completely different polymers. An acrylic label on clothing indicates the polymer is primarily made of PAN, in the US **acrylic** is used to describe fibres with a PAN content of >85%, **modacrylic** has a PAN content of 35-85%. It is often co-polymerised with other molecules, such as vinyl acetate and methyl methacrylate, and when combined with butadiene and styrene it creates the rigid plastic ABS.

In the NG-Plastics dataset, the initial FTIR classification done by SSW referred to acrylonitrile, not PAN. Acrylonitrile (the monomer) is a pungent flammable liquid, not a plastic. For clarity, samples listed as acrylonitrile were relabelled as PAN.

In FTIR, the nitrile group produces a highly distinctive $C\equiv N$ peak at 2240 cm^{-1} , a region that is typically devoid of vibrational peaks. Like other olefins, the ethylene backbone produces a pair of CH and CH_2 peaks at 1230 and 1450 cm^{-1} , and a pair of CH_2 peaks at 2880 and 2940 cm^{-1} . Almost all PAN samples in the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset exhibit an ester $C=O$ peak at $\sim 1740\text{ cm}^{-1}$, suggesting that most samples contain copolymer of PAN and either vinyl acetate or vinyl acrylate. The ratio of the $C=O$ and $C\equiv N$ peaks may be an indicator of the relative content of PAN in acrylic fibres, and the appearance of the $C\equiv N$ peak in other plastics may suggest the presence of acrylonitrile in their formulation.

5.7 Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS)

ABS is a commonly used block copolymer made from vinyl polymerisation of three olefins, acrylonitrile, butadiene, and styrene. Combining 3 units together imparts control over chemical resistance, flexibility, and toughness based on the proportions of each, making ABS a versatile plastic. ABS is primarily used for injection moulding of commercial objects that need to be resilient (toys, helmets, computer keyboards, pipes, automotive components, appliance casings, corrugated plastic sheeting). The styrene and butadiene parts of ABS make it susceptible to UV damage, and when exposed to sunlight it will degrade over time, turning yellow and brittle. In the absence of sunlight, or if UV-protective additives are used, ABS can be very resilient: relatively intact lego still routinely washes up on shore in the UK 25 years after a shipment was lost at sea [BBC News, 2023].

In FTIR, ABS is distinguishable by the combination of aromatic peaks from the styrene unit, the C≡N peak from acrylonitrile, and C=C peaks from butadiene. The styrene produces 2 benzene ring peaks at 700 and 760 cm^{-1} , and a set of aromatic C-H peaks between 3000 and 3100 cm^{-1} . The acrylonitrile produces a highly distinctive C≡N peak at 2240 cm^{-1} . The butadiene unit produces two C=C-H modes at 910 and 970 cm^{-1} , and the ethylene backbone of styrene and acrylonitrile is responsible for the CH and CH₂ modes at 1450 and 1490 cm^{-1} , and the CH₂ peaks at 2860 and 2920 cm^{-1} . The styrene peaks tend to be the strongest, reflecting the fact that most ABS formulations are ~50% styrene, but ABS can be distinguished from PS by the appearance of the C≡N peak at 2240 cm^{-1} .

5.8 Polyvinyl Acetate (PVAc, PVA)

Although it contains an ester, Polyvinyl Acetate is a polyolefin because it is produced by vinyl polymerisation, with the acetate being part of the side-group not the polymer backbone. It is sometimes referred to as PVA, which can cause confusion with polyvinyl alcohol (PVOH, sometimes also called PVA), so here Polyvinyl Acetate will be referred to as PVAc to make the distinction clearer. PVAc is primarily used by dispersing the microparticles of polymer in water that can be applied wet before drying into a clear solid. Its uses include as an adhesive for porous materials, a binding agent for water- and latex-based paints, and as a clear resin for manufacturing. When co-polymerised with ethylene it produces polyethylene vinyl acetate (PEVA), often used to make plastic foams and rubbers for clothing, padding, and furniture.

In FTIR, PVAc exhibits strong ester peaks as well as peaks from the ethylene backbone and the acetate CH_3 . The ester produces a strong $\text{C}=\text{O}$ at $\sim 1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a $\text{C}-\text{O}$ peak at $\sim 1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$; the ethylene backbone produces a CH_2 peak at 1440 cm^{-1} ; and the acetate produces a CH_3 peak at 1370 cm^{-1} . Polyvinyl acetate can be readily distinguished from polyvinyl alcohol by the appearance of the ester peaks, which do not occur in PVOH, and from PEVA by the lack of the distinctive pair of CH peaks that polyethylene produces at ~ 2850 and $\sim 2920\text{ cm}^{-1}$. PVAc can be difficult to distinguish from structurally similar polyacrylates. 7 out of 8 PVAc samples in the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset exhibit a set of narrow peaks between $3600\text{--}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ that are associated with aluminosilicate clay minerals.

5.9 Polyacrylate

Polyacrylates are a sub-class of polyolefins that have acrylate side-groups. Acrylate is very similar in structure to acetate, making polyacrylates similar to PVAc. **Acrylic paints, resins, and adhesives** often incorporate polyacrylate, but not all acrylics contain polyacrylate. **Acrylic glass** is a specific type of polyacrylate, polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) that forms a clear, transparent resin that is often used in place of glass where low weight and impact resistance are required, such as aircraft windows and hockey rink barriers. Polyacrylates are also used as binding agents in water-based and latex paints, and polycyanoacrylate is used as an adhesive in superglue.

In FTIR, Polyacrylates are typified by strong ester peaks, namely the C=O peak at 1730 cm^{-1} and a C-O peak at 1160 cm^{-1} . The absence of any other major functional groups makes them difficult to distinguish from structurally similar PVAc. At least 4 out of 28 samples classed as Polyacrylate in the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset contains a small proportion of acrylonitrile, indicated by the presence of a $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ peak at 2240 cm^{-1} , and two samples exhibit probable clay mineral peaks at $3600\text{-}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

6. Polyesters

Polyesters are a class of plastics made from polymerisation of carboxylic acids and alcohols/glycols to form ester linkages. Polyesters are a major plastic in the textile industry.

6.1 Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)

A commonly used polyester made from terephthalic acid and ethylene glycol, PET accounts for about 10% of all plastic production, and 70% of all polyester/polyamide/acrylic fibre production [Geyer *et al.*, 2017]. Rigid PET is best known for its use in packaging and plastic bottles, and most fabrics classed as polyester are made of PET fibre for its hydrophobic and thermal insulation properties. Dacron (fabric, sailcloth, wadding in jackets), fiberfill (wadding in jackets, cushions) and mylar (metalized film used in balloons and insulation) are all based on PET. Mylar and Dacron are also used in spacesuits because of their durability and thermal insulation qualities.

PET is distinguishable in FTIR by a combination of benzene ring, ester, and CH₂ peaks. The benzene ring produces a C-C peak at 1400 cm⁻¹; the ester produces a strong C=O peak at ~1725 cm⁻¹ and two strong C-O peaks at ~1100 and ~1250 cm⁻¹; and the ethylene sub-unit produces a strong CH₂ peak at ~730 cm⁻¹.

6.2 Alkyd

Alkyd is a generic term for polyester resins made from the condensation polymerisation of polyols (molecules containing 2 or more alcohol groups, such as glycerol) and polycarboxylic acids (molecules containing 2 or more carboxylic acid groups, such as phthalic acid). Alkyds are a commonly used binding agent in oil-based paints, varnishes, enamels, and flexible coatings. **Long-oil** alkyd resins are those that include a substantial proportion of unsaturated fatty acids for cross-linking, which promotes rapid drying. Because alkyd monomer units often contain more than 2 binding sites for polymerisation, alkyds tend to form highly cross-linked networks rather than long, linear chains.

In FTIR, the spectrum of alkyd is extremely variable, reflecting the variety of different monomers that may be used, but their commonalities include the ester C=O peak at 1730 cm^{-1} , a C-O peak at 1280 cm^{-1} , and a pair of CH₂ peaks at 2860 and 2930 cm^{-1} . A broad O-H peak around $3000\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of residual alcohol groups due to incomplete polymerisation, and 2 out of 42 samples of alkyd in the NG-Plastics FTIR Dataset exhibits probable clay mineral peaks between 3600 and 3700 cm^{-1} .

7. Polyamides

Polyamides are typically made from the condensation polymerisation of carboxylic acids and amines to form amide linkages. Synthetic polyamides are collectively referred to as Nylons, and like polyesters, they are a major plastic in the textile industry [Geyer *et al.*, 2017]. Natural, non-synthetic polyamides also exist: biological protein is a polyamide made by living organisms from chains of amino acids. There are two major forms of nylon: aromatic and aliphatic, depending on whether the monomers include aromatic rings or not. Aromatic polyamides are often referred to as Aramids, and as aliphatic nylons are the most common type, I will use the term Nylon to refer to aliphatic polyamides exclusively.

7.1 Nylon

Aliphatic nylon is the most common form of Nylon, and technically encompasses several different synthetic polyamides made from short chain monomers, such as caprolactam, adipic acid, and hexamethylenediamine. The number in the nylon name, e.g. Nylon-6, indicates the length of the monomer unit, and a double number (e.g. Nylon-6,6) indicates the use of two monomers of different lengths. Nylon can be moulded for use in rigid objects but is predominantly made as fibres for use in textiles (especially clothing) and as monofilaments (fishing lines & guitar strings). Making Nylon is a common experiment in undergraduate chemistry training.

In FTIR, aliphatic Nylon is typified by the amide C=O peak at 1640 cm^{-1} , the N-H peak at 1550 cm^{-1} , two CH₂ peaks at 2860 and 2930 cm^{-1} , and a broad, N-H peak between 3200 and 3400 cm^{-1} . It can be possible to distinguish different forms of Nylon based on small variances in FTIR, but evaluation of environmental samples may be confounded by other factors such as weathering and biological contamination.

7.2 Aramid

Aramid encompasses all synthetic polyamides made from chains of aromatic rings connected by amide linkages. They are less common than aliphatic Nylons but tend to have superior strength, abrasion resistance, and heat resistance, making them ideal for use in body armour, flame-resistant clothing, and mooring ropes. Kevlar is an example of a **para-aramid**, where the amide linkages are on opposite corners of the aromatic ring, Nomex is a **meta-aramid**, where the linkages are on corners separated by one atom. Because they contain aromatic rings that readily absorb UV light, aramids tend to degrade when exposed to sunlight unless UV-blocking additives are included in the plastic.

In FTIR, aramids are typified by a combination of two amide peaks (C=O and N-H at 1660 and 1540 cm^{-1}) and either one or two aromatic ring peaks depending on whether the aramid is **para** or **meta**. Para-aramids exhibit a single benzene ring peak at 1515 cm^{-1} , while meta-aramids exhibit two peaks at 1490 and 1610 cm^{-1} . The single example of aramid in the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset is a good match for a meta-aramid such as Nomex.

8. Polyurethanes (PU, PUR)

PU is a polymer class based on formation of carbamate (urethane) linkages between a diisocyanate and a diol, and like Nylon it can include many different polymers depending on which monomers are used. Overall, PU accounts for about 8% of global non-fibre plastic production to date [Geyer *et al.*, 2017] and is mainly used as flexible foam (e.g. kitchen sponges, wadding in furniture), rigid foam (thermal insulation), or as an elastic fibre for clothing sold under the names Spandex, Lycra, and elastane.

In FTIR, PU appears to be a combination of polyester and polyamide, with a C=O peak at 1730 cm^{-1} , a relatively weak N-H peak at 1600 cm^{-1} and an N-H peak at $3200\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and a C-O peak at 1220 cm^{-1} . Polyurethanes can be distinguished from polyamides by the presence of the C-O peak and the position of the C=O peak, which is $<1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for polyamide, $>1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for polyurethanes and polyesters. Polyurethanes can then be distinguished from polyesters by the presence of the N-H peaks at 1600 and $\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. 1 out of 8 PU samples in the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset also exhibits clay mineral peaks between 3600 and 3700 cm^{-1} .

9. Polycarbonates (PC)

PC is another polymer class based on formation of carbonate linkages. The most common polycarbonate polymer is made from the monomer bisphenol A (*aka* BPA, a known endocrine disruptor). Polycarbonates tend to be highly transparent, durable, and impact-resistant, and are typically used to make sheet roofing, CDs, heavy-duty bottles, and durable windows/lenses (including laboratory goggles, windscreens, and lighting canopies). Because many PCs contain aromatic rings that readily absorb UV light, they tend to degrade when exposed to sunlight unless UV-blocking additives are included in the plastic.

In FTIR, PC is distinguished by the presence of a carbonate C=O peak at $\sim 1760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and several overlapping C-O-C peaks between 1100 and 1300 cm^{-1} . PCs based on aromatic rings, such as BPA-based PC also have sharp benzene peaks at ~ 1010 and $\sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$; the 6 examples labelled as PC in the NG-Plastics FTIR dataset all exhibit aromatic peaks as well as a second C=O peak at 1720 cm^{-1} , suggesting that they are a mix of bisphenol-based polycarbonate and polyester, probably pieces of polycarbonate plastic that have been coated with a polyester paint.

10. Polyethers

Polyethers are a class of polymers based on ether linkages, which can be made by condensation of polyols, aldehydes, or cyclic ethers. Polyethylene glycol (known as PEG, PEO, POE depending on context) is probably the most well-known polyether, used extensively as a binding agent in medicines, skin creams, lubricants, and as an additive in other plastics to impart greater elasticity.

10.1 POM (Polyformaldehyde, Polyacetal, Acetal)

POM is a relatively uncommon plastic made from polymerisation of formaldehyde. POM is typically used for high strength, low friction applications such as ball bearings, plumbing joints, gears, and labware. The children's construction toy K'Nex is made of POM.

In FTIR, POM has a relatively simple spectrum dominated by two C-O-C peaks at 900/940 cm^{-1} and a C-O-C peak at 1100 cm^{-1} . The relatively narrow peak at 1240 cm^{-1} is a CH_2 peak, and two CH_2 peaks appear at 2920 and 2980 cm^{-1} .

11. Biological Polymers

Humans are not the only species on Earth that use polymers. All living things employ biologically manufactured polymers in important roles, including giving cells structure (e.g. cellulose), genetic data storage (e.g. DNA), signalling (e.g. peptides), and as biochemical machinery (e.g. proteins). Natural materials made predominantly from biological polymers such as wool, cotton, and rubber have been used by humans for millennia. Because of the prevalence of biological polymers in the natural environment and their use as industrial materials, objects made of biological polymers can sometimes be mistaken for synthetic plastics based on appearance and form. Examples in the NG-Plastics dataset include proteins (a form of polyamide) and cellulose and chitin (two forms of polysaccharide). Biological polymers can also be modified chemically to make semi-synthetic polymers (see Section 12).

11.1 Proteinaceous Polyamides (Protein)

Living organisms produce a wide variety of polyamides, including **peptides**, **polypeptides**, and **proteins** (these are just labels for different lengths of polyamide chain, with peptides being the shortest and proteins being the longest). All are made from the controlled condensation polymerisation of 22 proteinogenic (protein-forming) amino acids in specific sequences depending on function. For simplicity, I will refer to all natural (non-synthetic) polyamides as protein. Protein is ubiquitous within living organisms and is often observed in environmental samples, either as a biological contaminant on top of synthetic materials (such as a biofilm [Razzell Hollis *et al.*, 2024] or as a material in its own right (such as keratin and collagen).

In FTIR, protein is distinguished by two very strong amide peaks, the C=O peak at 1650 cm^{-1} and the N-H peak at 1520 cm^{-1} . A broad N-H peak is seen between 3000 and 3500 cm^{-1} , as are two or more weak C-H peaks between 2800 and 3000 cm^{-1} . The many possible sequences of amino acids in protein means that there is substantial variation in the rest of the FTIR spectrum, and in samples where protein is part of a larger biological matrix (e.g. cells and biofilms), it is often accompanied by carbohydrates that have several broad, overlapping peaks between 900 and 1200 cm^{-1} . The amide peaks make protein appear very similar to other polyamides, specifically Nylon, which can lead to confusion. However, the peaks of protein tend to be broader than those of Nylon, due to the greater diversity of amide bonds present in protein.

11.2 Cellulose

Cellulose is a biological polymer in the polysaccharide class, made from condensation of glucose units into long linear chains linked by ether groups. Cellulose provides structure to many plants and is the primary component of materials such as cotton, paper, and cardboard. Cellulose is also a precursor to several semi-synthetic plastics, including cellulose acetate (used in modern film stock, cigarette filters), and nitrocellulose (or celluloid, mainly used in old film stock and gun-cotton). Cellophane sheets and viscose fibres (also known as rayon) are made by the solvent extraction of cellulose from plant matter.

In FTIR, Cellulose is distinguished by a set of overlapping peaks between 950 and 1200 cm^{-1} with a maximum typically around 1060 cm^{-1} , which are attributable to the various CH modes of the glucose ring. It also tends to have a very strong broad O-H peak between 3100 and 3600 cm^{-1} due to the various OH groups of glucose.

11.4 Chitin

Chitin is another biological polysaccharide, produced by the condensation of N-acetylglucosamine, essentially a sugar modified with an amide side-group. Chitin is typically found in the exoskeletons of insects and crustaceans, the beaks and gladii of molluscs, and as a component of structural tissue in other animals. Powdered chitin is used as an additive in food processing and in fertiliser. It should not be confused with keratin, which is also a structural biopolymer (found in hair, fingernails, claws, feathers) that is made from proteins, not sugars. Chitin is readily distinguished from cellulose in FTIR by the presence of the amide C=O and N-H peaks at 1650 and 1520 cm^{-1} , and the amide N-H peak at $\sim 3250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

There are no conclusively chitinous spectra in the NG dataset.

12. Semi-Synthetic Polymers

The earliest plastics developed by industrial chemists were in fact made by chemically modifying existing biological polymers to improve or otherwise alter their material properties for specific purposes. The resulting polymers are now classed as **semi-synthetic**, and most are modifications of cellulose (the primary polymer in cotton). Their similarity to the original biological polymer can make identification more difficult, but when additional functional groups are added (such as in cellulose acetate), any new FTIR peaks produced by those extra groups can be used to distinguish the semi-synthetic material from the biological one.

12.1 Viscose / Rayon / Cellophane

Viscose-based materials (including Rayon textile fibres and Cellophane films) are a semi-synthetic polymer made from solvent-extraction of cellulose from plant fibres. The cellulose structure is regenerated at the end of the process, meaning that Viscose is chemically identical to Cellulose. This can make them very difficult to distinguish via FTIR, the only reported differences are alteration of the OH band shape around 3300 cm^{-1} and the loss of some very minor peaks [Geminiani *et al.*, 2022].

12.2 Cellulose Acetate (CA)

CA is a semi-synthetic polysaccharide made by the esterification of natural Cellulose, where one or more OH side groups of the glucose backbone have been modified into acetate groups. It can be distinguished from Cellulose by the intensity of the ester C=O peak at $\sim 1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is non-existent in pure Cellulose, weak in degraded Cellulose, and strong in CA. We only have one example of CA in the NG-Plastics dataset.

12.3 Nitrocellulose

Nitrocellulose is a nitrated cellulose polymer, where one or more OH side groups of the glucose backbone have been modified into nitro groups. Nitrocellulose is highly flammable, hence its use in gun-cotton, but was also used in film stock and lacquers until the mid-20th century. It is easily distinguished from Cellulose by the presence of NO₂ peaks at 1650, 1280 cm⁻¹, and 840 cm⁻¹.

13. Tricky Material Categories

These are categories that are poorly defined, chemically speaking, and may overlap significantly with each other in terms of both composition and FTIR spectra, making them difficult to distinguish.

13.1 Polyepoxide (Epoxy)

Epoxy refers to the polyepoxides class, polymers made by the epoxidation of various molecules, most commonly bisphenol A (BPA, a known endocrine disruptor). Epoxidation is the creation of epoxide (or oxirane) groups, which then polymerise by reacting with functional groups on other molecules, producing ethers/esters/amides, depending on the molecule. This variety can make identifying epoxy resins very difficult by FTIR spectroscopy alone. Epoxy resins tend to be soft thermoplastics until they are cured by further reaction with a curing/hardening agent, such as triamine, that promotes cross-linking between chains to improve the resin's thermal and mechanical properties. Epoxy resins are often used as powder coatings, adhesives, and as a binding matrix in composite materials such as fibreglass and carbon fibre. As a result, their use also overlaps significantly with other polymers such as polyacrylates, polyesters, and polyurethanes.

In FTIR, uncured epoxy exhibits distinctive C-O-C ring peaks from the oxirane group at 830 and 910 cm^{-1} , while cured epoxy does not. Bisphenol- and Novolac-based resins will exhibit aromatic ring peaks at 1510 and 1600 cm^{-1} . 2 samples are listed as epoxy in the NG-Plastics FTIR Dataset, both appear to be cured epoxy ether resins with slightly different formulations.

13.2 Acrylic

Acrylic is a commonly used term that can refer to several different polymers that use monomers ultimately derived from acrylic acid. **Acrylic paints, resins, and adhesives** usually involve polyacrylate polymers, while **acrylic fibres** and textiles are usually of a significant percentage of polyacrylonitrile (PAN). **Acrylic glass** refers specifically to the polyacrylate PMMA. Unfortunately, any of these will often just be referred to as 'acrylic', which can lead to confusion, but the object's morphology and usage (textile vs glass vs paint) can point towards the use of a specific polymer, which can then be confirmed by FTIR.

In the NG-Plastics dataset, 'Acrylic' was one of the labels used by SSW during their initial classification of spectra. All of these samples appear to be polyacrylates rather than PAN (see section 5.8) and have been relabelled as such.

14. Glossary of Terms

ABS	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
Acrylic	Depends on context, usually refers to polyacrylate (as resin, paint, adhesive), PMMA (as glass), or PAN (as textile/fibre)
Adhesive	Generic term for any binding agent used to affix two surfaces to one another
Atactic	Describes polymers where chiral side-groups are positioned randomly on either side of the backbone
ATR-FTIR	Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy
Backbone	The primary chain of atoms that makes up a polymer's length
Biological Polymer	A polymer made by an exclusively biological process, e.g. protein
BPA	Bisphenol A, a monomer used in the production of some polycarbonates and polyepoxides
CA	Cellulose Acetate
Copolymer	A polymer made of two or more types of repeating units. Depending on their order, can be alternating, block, or random.
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene
HDPE	High Density Polyethylene
FTIR	Fourier-Transform Infrared spectroscopy
Homopolymer	A polymer made of a single type of repeating unit
Isotactic	Describes polymers where chiral side-groups all are all positioned on the same side of the backbone
LDPE	Low Density Polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear Low Density Polyethylene
MDPE	Medium Density Polyethylene
Monomer	The original molecule that is reacted together with other monomers during polymerisation, becoming the repeating units in the resulting polymer.
Paint	Generic term for any liquid containing pigment and a binding agent that is intended to be applied to a surface to provide coloration
PAN	Polyacrylonitrile
PANI	Polyaniline
PC	Polycarbonate
PE	Polyethylene
PEG	Polyethylene Glycol (also PEO, POE)
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PEVA	Polyethylene Vinyl Acetate
Plastic	A material made primarily of synthetic or semi-synthetic polymers
PMMA	Polymethyl methacrylate
Polymer	A long single-molecule chain formed of hundreds to thousands of repeating units joined together during polymerisation
Polymerisation	The chemical reaction that joins monomers together into a polymer chain. There are many different kinds of polymerisation reaction that work with different monomers
Polyolefin	Polymers made from olefins (alkenes)

POM	Polyoxymethylene
PP	Polypropylene
PS	Polystyrene
PU	Polyurethane
PUR	Polyurethane
PVA	Polyvinyl acetate, sometimes polyvinyl alcohol
PVAc	Polyvinyl acetate
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
PVOH	Polyvinyl alcohol
Resin	Generic term for any liquid that then irreversibly hardens through polymerisation to form a solid mass, also refers to the product
Semi-Synthetic Polymer	A polymer originally made by a biological process, e.g. cellulose, that was then modified using industrial chemistry, e.g. turning it into cellulose acetate
Side-group	Any functional groups of atoms that do not make up the central backbone of a polymer. Side-groups in proteins are called residues
Syndiotactic	Describes polymers where chiral side-groups are on alternating sides of the backbone
Synthetic Polymer	A polymer made by an exclusively industrial process, e.g. Nylon. This applies even when the monomers are made from a natural source, such as fossil fuels
SSW	Surface Science Western, the lab contracted to acquire much of the FTIR spectra shown in this Primer
UV	Ultraviolet light (wavelength range: 10–415 nm)

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